

Intake of Levonorgestrel Caused an Increase in Inflammatory Markers in the Reproductive Organs of Female Wistar Rats

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Abstract

The incessant intake of contraceptives among young adults is a cause for concern as a result of increased sexual activity. This study assessed the levels of some proinflammatory biomarkers associated with incessant intake of levonorgestrel (LNG) in the uterus and ovaries and the outcome of drug withdrawal using a rat model. Sixty female Wistar rats weighing 110 - 120 g were purchased and acclimatized for 28 days and kept in suitable environmental conditions. They had access to rat's pellets and clean water *ad libitum*. They were randomized into three groups (n = 20); groups A and B were administered 1.83 mg/kg bodyweight (BW) of LNG orally once and twice-weekly respectively, while group C served as the control. Five animals from each group were sacrificed at 30, 60, and 90 days. The remaining were observed for a 30-day post-treatment for possible recovery. The uterus and ovaries were excised, homogenized and centrifuged. The level of tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), nuclear factor and kappa B (NF- κ B), was determined using enzyme-linked immune-sorbent assay. Results showed a significant increase in TNF- α and NF- κ B, especially in the group administered LNG twice-weekly. Also, both proinflammatory markers were significantly upregulated in the uterus than in the ovaries. Recovery was observed only in TNF- α in the ovary of the once-weekly group. The uterus was more affected, and animals exposed to LNG twice-weekly suffered more assaults. The prolonged intake of levonorgestrel is detrimental to the integrity and function of these important reproductive organs

Keywords: Levonorgestrel; Inflammation; Oxidative stress; Contraceptives; uterus; ovary; reproductive abnormalities

INTRODUCTION

The total well-being physically, emotionally, behaviourally, and in the social aspects of life, termed reproductive and sexual health is a global concern. The reproductive and sexual health of women is seriously challenged by several gynecological abnormalities worldwide. Crucial contributors to these are physiological processes that increase the markers of inflammation (Agarwal *et al.*, 2012), which contribute to reproductive abnormalities (Pyeon *et al.*, 2021). This is because ROS damages the oocytes, causes a decline in oocyte quality, modulate estrogen receptors, leads to luteal regression, inhibits steroidogenesis in the corpus luteum,

inhibits folliculogenesis, which are associated with the incidence of reproductive anomalies (Phang *et al.*, 2023).

Inflammation is a process that significantly contribute to the onset of many diseases. Increased levels of these biomarkers are associated with increased risk and severity in these conditions. They have also been shown to also potentially impacting their incidence and progression. Inflammation has been greatly contributed to by hormonal modulation resulting from several factors, including synthetic hormones (Furman *et al.*, 2019). One such is hormonal emergency contraceptive pills (ECPs), which are increasingly used as a result of increased sexual activities among young adults. Although known for multiple advantages such as high effectiveness, accessibility, and non-invasiveness, ECPs are associated with several challenges, and these include lack of information or misinformation, negative past experiences, mixed feelings about side effects among others.

Several methods have been developed to prevent pregnancy including the use of devices (such as implants, injections, patches, vaginal rings, intrauterine devices) and oral pills (containing progestin, estradiol or a combination of both). Oral pills used in emergency situations up to about 72 hours after sexual intercourse to prevent pregnancy are called emergency contraceptives. Levonorgestrel (LNG) is a widely used synthetic progestin found in hormonal contraceptives, including emergency contraception, intrauterine devices (IUDs), and combined oral contraceptives (Crawford *et al.*, 2021). While LNG is highly effective in preventing unintended pregnancies, reducing the risks associated with abortions, and decreasing maternal and child mortality, its prolonged use has raised concerns regarding potential adverse effects on reproductive health. Additionally, they have been linked also with clotting disorders, behavioural changes (Batres *et al.*, 2018), hormonal imbalances and this has been studied to promote the onset of cervical and breast cancer, and thrombosis (Shukla *et al.*, 2017). Despite the widespread use of LNG-based contraceptives, there remains a need to better understand their long-term impact on female reproductive organs, particularly the uterus and ovaries, which play vital roles in fertility and hormonal regulation.

The induction of chronic inflammation in reproductive tissues will alter redox homeostasis, leading to increased lipid peroxidation, DNA damage, and mitochondrial dysfunction (Yan *et al.*, 2022). These can affect a variety of physiologic functions and pathologic processes involving the female reproductive tracts such as oocyte reserve, folliculogenesis, ovarian steroidogenesis, and ovulation (Aslan *et al.*, 2025). The uterus and ovaries, being highly sensitive to hormonal fluctuations, may suffer from oxidative damage, which could compromise their normal function and structure. Given these concerns, it is critical to investigate whether prolonged LNG intake influences TNF- α , NF- κ B, and oxidative stress biomarkers in the reproductive system. By analyzing the impact of LNG on inflammatory markers in the uterus and ovary, this study aims to provide crucial insights into the potential risks associated with prolonged hormonal contraceptive use and the effects of drug withdrawal. Understanding these mechanisms could aid in developing strategies to mitigate adverse effects and ensure safer contraceptive options for women.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Design, Sacrifice of Animals, Homogenization and Centrifugation

Sixty (60) female rats of the Wistar strain weighing between 110g and 150g were used for the study and acclimatized for a period of 28 days in the departmental animal house under suitable environmental conditions in plastic cages with wire nets for 28 days. They were purchased

from the Physiology Department of the University of Ibadan, Nigeria. They were randomly assigned into three (3) groups of twenty animals each ($n = 20$). All the animals were allowed equal access to food, and water *ad libitum*. The animals were handled in compliance with the National Institutes of Health guidelines for the care and use of animals in research [19]. The treatments of the animals lasted for a period of ninety (90) days. The animals in Group A (Once Weekly) were orally administered 1.83 mg/Kg BW LNG one day in a week at a 12-hour interval (morning at 7 a.m. and evening at 6 p.m.). Group B (Twice Weekly) animals were orally administered LNG at a dose of 1.83 mg/Kg BW two days in a week, Group C, the control group, was orally administered normal saline, the same volume used as the vehicle for the drug in the treated groups, at the same time as the treated groups. After 30 days of treatment, five (5) animals from each group were sacrificed by cervical decapitation. The tissues of interest, namely the ovaries, and uterus, were harvested, homogenized (ice-cold Phosphate buffer, 0.1M, pH 7.4) using Teflon homogenizer to make 2 % homogenate and centrifuged at 10,000 g for 10 minutes in a Microfield refrigerated centrifuge (Model: MF – TGL16) at 4 °C to obtain the post-mitochondrial fractions and stored for biochemical analysis. This procedure was repeated at 60, and 90 days respectively. The remaining five animals in each group were left for a 30-day post-treatment recovery period. Thereafter, they were sacrificed, tissues were processed and analyses were carried out on the harvested and processed tissues.

Determination of Proinflammatory Markers

The quantitative determination of Tumor Necrosis Factor- α (TNF- α) and Nuclear Factor Kappa B (NF- κ B) in uterus, and ovaries were assayed using a Microplate Immunoenzymometric assay (ELISA) whose kits was supplied by Mornmed Medical Equipment Company Limited, United Kingdom.

Statistical Analysis

Data obtained was expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), $n = 5$, using Graph Pad Prism version 9. Treated and control groups were compared using row statistics and 2- way ANOVA (multiple comparison TUKEY test). Statistical significance was set at 95 % confidence level ($p < 0.05$). α showed a statistical significance when once weekly was compared with control ($p < 0.05$). β indicated a statistical significance when once weekly was compared with those treated twice weekly ($p < 0.05$). γ showed significance when twice weekly was compared with control ($p < 0.05$).

RESULTS

Effect of LNG Intake on the Concentration of Nuclear Factor -Kappa B (NF- κ B) in the Reproductive Organs of Wistar Rats

The concentration of NF- κ B was measured in the uterus (figure 1) and ovary (figure 2) of the Wistar rats treated with LNG was compared with control. A significant increase that was dependent on the dose and period of administration was observed ($p < 0.05$). After the drug was stopped for 30 days (30 days recovery period), the concentration of NF- κ B was not reversed in the uterus in both treated groups but further increased. Meanwhile in the ovary, the increase in NF- κ B observed was reversed in both treated groups after drug withdrawal.

Effect of LNG Intake on the Concentration of Tumor Necrosis Factor-alpha (TNF- α) in the Reproductive Organs of Wistar Rats

The concentration of TNF- α determined in the uterus (figure 3) and ovary (figure 4) of the Wistar rats treated with LNG was compared with control. A significant increase that was dependent on the dose and period of administration was observed ($p < 0.05$). After the drug was withdrawn, the uterus experienced a remarkable decline in the level of TNF- α both in once weekly and twice weekly groups while the ovary, both treated groups maintained the same level of TNF- α as seen at 90 days.

DISCUSSION

This study investigated the inflammatory effects of prolonged levonorgestrel (LNG) administration in female Wistar rats, with a focus on its impact on key proinflammatory cytokines—Tumor Necrosis Factor-alpha (TNF- α) and Nuclear Factor-kappa B (NF- κ B)—in the uterus and ovaries. Results show a clear dose- and duration-dependent proinflammatory and pro-oxidative response, which was only partially reversible after stopping weekly LNG treatment.

The observed upregulation of TNF- α and NF- κ B in the uterus and ovaries, especially in the twice-weekly LNG group, indicates the activation of inflammatory pathways associated with prolonged hormonal stimulation. TNF- α , produced predominantly by activated macrophages, plays a central role in initiating and sustaining inflammatory cascades in reproductive tissues. Elevated levels of this cytokine have been correlated with several reproductive disorders such as endometriosis, polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), and immunological infertility (John-Olabode *et al.*, 2025; Muisi *et al.*, 2022). The persistent elevation of NF- κ B observed even after the 30-day withdrawal period in the uterus further suggests potential for long-term inflammatory imprinting or impaired resolution mechanisms. NF- κ B, being a transcription factor that regulates numerous genes related to immune and stress responses, may exacerbate tissue damage when hyperactivated, contributing to chronic reproductive dysfunction (Gao *et al.*, 2025).

Notably, the uterus appeared more susceptible than the ovary, which may reflect differences in tissue-specific metabolism, hormone receptor density, or inflammatory sensitivity. Interestingly, while some degree of recovery was observed in TNF- α , particularly in the once-weekly group, this improvement was either absent or minimal in the twice-weekly treatment group. This finding implies a threshold effect, where frequent exposure to LNG surpasses the organ's ability to recover fully, even after cessation of exposure. This may induce long-lasting or potentially irreversible cellular changes, such as mitochondrial dysfunction or membrane instability.

These results are consistent with prior evidence linking synthetic progestins to redox imbalance and reproductive toxicity. Studies have shown that chronic hormone administration can impair mitochondrial function, dysregulate apoptosis, and alter cytokine expression in estrogen- and progesterone-sensitive tissues (Shukla *et al.*, 2025; Batres *et al.*, 2018). Cauci *et al.*, 2021 observed an increase in inflammation in response to intake of combined oral contraceptives. Our findings contribute further by delineating how different dosing frequencies of LNG impact the severity and reversibility of such effects.

From a translational perspective, the findings raise important concerns about the off-label or frequent use of emergency contraceptive pills among young women. While LNG is generally safe when used occasionally, repeated and unmonitored intake, as reflected in the twice-weekly

group, may predispose individuals to chronic inflammation, oxidative damage, and reproductive dysfunction, potentially affecting fertility, endometrial health, and menstrual regulation. More importantly because despite advances in the diagnosis, prevention, and treatment of gynecological abnormalities, there are still increased mortality and morbidity in females as an outcome of high prevalence and incidence of cancers of the reproductive organs, unexplained infertility, uterine fibroids, endometriosis, and polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS).

CONCLUSION

Prolonged and frequent intake of levonorgestrel induces significant inflammatory responses in the uterus and ovaries of female Wistar rats. These effects were more severe and less reversible with increased dosing frequency, underscoring the risks associated with the habitual use of emergency contraceptives. These findings advocate for increased public health education on the appropriate use of LNG, further research into its long-term reproductive safety, and potential mitigation strategies to safeguard female reproductive health

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